

Osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of 6-aminopenicillanic acid by diperioatoargentate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium by stopped flow technique

S. D. Gunagi, S. T. Nandibewoor and S. A. Chimatadar*

P.G. Department of Studies in Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003, Karnataka, India

E-mail : schimatadar@gmail.com

Manuscript received 06 September 2010, revised 30 December 2010, accepted 30 December 2010

Abstract : The kinetics of micro amounts (10^{-7} mol dm^{-3}) of osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of 6-aminopenicillanic acid by diperioatoargentate(III) in alkaline medium at 25 °C and at a constant ionic strength of 0.04 mol dm^{-3} was studied spectrophotometrically. The oxidation products were confirmed by IR, LC-ESI-MS and NMR spectral studies as 2-formyl-5,5-dimethylthiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid and silver(I). The stoichiometry is 1 : 1 i.e. one mole of diperioatoargentate(III) requires one mole of 6-aminopenicillanic acid. The reaction is first order with respect to diperioatoargentate(III) and catalyst, osmium(VIII) concentrations, whereas less than unit order in both 6-aminopenicillanic acid and alkali. The oxidation reaction in alkaline medium has been shown to proceed via a osmium(VIII)-6-aminopenicillanic acid complex, which further reacts with one molecule of monoperioatoargentate(III) in a rate determining step followed by other fast steps. The active species of catalyst and oxidant have been identified and a suitable mechanism is proposed. The reaction constants involved in the different steps of the mechanism were calculated. The catalytic constant (K_c) was also calculated at 25 °C. The activation parameters with respect to slow step of the mechanism were computed and discussed. The thermodynamic quantities were also determined.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, 6-aminopenicillanic acid, diperioatoargentate(III), osmium(VIII).

Introduction

Amino acids act not only as the building blocks in protein synthesis but they also play significant role in the metabolism. Amino acids can undergo many types of reactions and the oxidation products differ for different oxidants^{1,2}. Thus, the study of amino acids becomes important because of their biological significance and selectivity towards the oxidant. 6-Aminopenicillanic acid (6-APA) is an essential amino acid and the oxidation of it may help in understanding some aspects of kinetics.

Diperioatoargentate(III) is a powerful oxidizing agent in alkaline medium with the reduction potential³ 1.74 V. It is widely used as a volumetric reagent for the determination of various organic and inorganic species⁴. Jayprakash Rao *et al.* have used DPA as an oxidizing agent for the kinetics of oxidation of various organic substrates⁵. They normally found the order with respect to both oxidant and substrate was unity and OH^- ion concentration was found to enhance the rate of reaction. It was also observed that they did not arrive the possible active species of diperioatoargentate(III) in alkali and on

the other hand they proposed mechanisms by generalizing the diperioatoargentate(III) as $[\text{Ag}(\text{HL})\text{L}]^{(x+1)-}$, where L is a periodate with an uncertain number of protons and HL is a protonated periodate of an uncertain number of protons. However, Kumar *et al.* put an effort⁶ to give an evidence for the reactive form of diperioatoargentate(III) in the large scale of alkaline pH. In the present investigation, the authors have obtained the evidence for the reactive species for diperioatoargentate(III) in alkaline medium.

In recent years the use of transition metal ions such as osmium, ruthenium and iridium, either alone or as binary mixtures, as catalyst in various redox processes has attracted considerable interest⁷. The role of osmium(VIII) as a catalyst in some redox reactions has been reviewed⁸. Although the mechanism of catalysis depends on the nature of the substrate, the oxidant and experimental conditions, it has been shown that metal ions act as catalyst by one of these different paths such as the formation of complexes with reactants or oxidation of the substrate itself or through the formation of free radicals⁹. Osmium(VIII)

Gunagi *et al.* : Osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of 6-aminopenicillanic acid by diperiodatoargentate(III) *etc.*

Fig. 1. Chromatogram and LC-ESI-MS spectra of the product, 2-formyl-5,5-dimethylthiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of the product, 2-formyl-5,5-dimethylthiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid.

Fig. 3. First order plots for the osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of 6-aminopenicillanic acid by diperioatoargentate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium at 25 °C; [DPA] × 10⁵ mol dm⁻³ = (1) 1.0; (2) 3.0; (3) 5.0; (4) 7.0; (5) 10.0.

k_c values increased with increase in the concentration of 6-aminopenicillanic acid with less than unit order dependence (Table 1). The effect of potassium hydroxide concentration on the reaction rate was studied in the range of 4.0×10^{-3} to 4.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of diperioatoargentate(III), 6-aminopenicillanic

acid, osmium(VIII) and at a constant ionic strength of 0.04 mol dm⁻³. The rate constants increased with increase in alkali concentration (Table 1) and the order was found to be less than unity. Periodate concentration was varied from 1.0×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of reactants and at other constant con-

Table 1. Effect of variations of DPA, 6-APA, OH⁻, IO₄⁻ and Os^{VIII} concentrations on the osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of 6-APA by DPA in alkaline medium at 25 °C, $I = 0.04$ mol dm⁻³

[DPA] × 10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	[6-APA] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[OH ⁻] × 10 (mol dm ⁻³)	[IO ₄ ⁻] × 10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Os ^{VIII}] × 10 ⁷ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_c \times 10^2$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.6
3.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.7
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.8
7.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.7
10.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.8
5.0	1.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	0.5
5.0	3.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.3
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.8
5.0	7.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	2.3
5.0	10.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	2.7
5.0	5.0	0.04	1.0	5.0	1.0
5.0	5.0	0.08	1.0	5.0	1.4
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.8
5.0	5.0	0.3	1.0	5.0	1.9
5.0	5.0	0.4	1.0	5.0	2.1

Table-1 (contd.)

5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.8
5.0	5.0	0.2	3.0	5.0	1.3
5.0	5.0	0.2	5.0	5.0	1.0
5.0	5.0	0.2	7.0	5.0	0.8
5.0	5.0	0.2	10.0	5.0	0.6
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	0.0	0.19
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	1.0	0.52
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	3.0	1.3
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	5.0	1.7
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	7.0	3.0
5.0	5.0	0.2	1.0	10.0	4.2

ditions. It was observed that rate decreased with increasing periodate concentration (Table 1). At constant oxidant, reductant, alkali and at constant ionic strength, the catalyst, osmium(VIII) concentration was varied between 1.0×10^{-7} and 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³. As the osmium(VIII) concentration increases the rate also increases (Table 1). The order with respect to osmium(VIII) concentration was found to be unity.

The effect of initially added products, Ag^I and 2-formyl-5,5-dimethylthiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid were studied at constant oxidant, reductant, catalyst and at constant ionic strength and found that they did not affect the rate of reaction.

At constant concentrations of reactants, catalyst and at other constant conditions, the ionic strength was varied by varying the concentration of potassium nitrate. At constant alkali and other constant conditions, the effect of dielectric constant was studied by varying the *t*-butyl alcohol. It was found that, both ionic strength and effect of dielectric constant did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

The intervention of free radicals was examined as follows, the reaction mixture, to which a known quantity of acrylonitrile (scavenger) has been added initially, was kept in inert atmosphere for 3 h. Upon diluting the reaction mixture with methanol, precipitate resulted, suggesting there is participation of free radicals in the reaction.

Effect of initially added products :

In presence of osmium(VIII), the reaction was studied at 15, 20, 25 and 30 °C and it was observed that, as the temperature increased the rate of reaction also increased. The rate constant, *k* with respect to slow step of Scheme I^{*} were obtained from the slopes and intercepts of the plot of $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]/k_c$ versus $1/[\text{6-APA}]$, $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]/k_c$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]/k_c$ versus $[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]$ at 15, 20, 25 and 30 °C

(Table 2). The energy of activation was obtained by the Arrhenius plot, log *k* versus $1/T$, from which the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

It has been pointed out by Moelwyn-Hughes¹¹ that, in the presence of catalyst, the uncatalysed and catalysed reactions proceed simultaneously, so that

$$k_c = k_u + K_c [\text{catalyst}]^x$$

where *k_c* is the observed pseudo-first order rate constant in the presence of catalyst, *k_u* is the pseudo-first order rate constant in the absence of catalyst, *K_c* is the catalytic constant and 'x' is the order with respect to catalyst. Then the value of *K_c* is calculated by using the following equation :

$$K_c = \frac{k_c - k_u}{[\text{catalyst}]^x}$$

In the present study the value of 'x' is unity, so

$$K_c = \frac{1.7 \times 10^{-2} - 0.19 \times 10^{-2}}{[5.0 \times 10^{-7}]^1} = 30200$$

For the present experimental conditions and for the standard kinetic run the *K_c* was found to be 30200.

The literature survey reveals that the water soluble diperiodatoargentate(III) (DPA) has a formula $[\text{Ag}(\text{IO}_6)_2]^{7-}$ with dsp² configuration of square planar structure, similar to diperiodatocopper(III) complex with two bidentate ligands, periodate to form a planar molecule¹². When the same molecule is used in alkaline medium, it is unlike to be existed as $[\text{Ag}(\text{IO}_6)_2]^{7-}$ as periodate is known to be in various protonated forms depending on pH of the solution¹³ as given in following multiple equilibria (2)–(4).

Periodic acid exists as H_5IO_6 and as H_4IO_6^- at pH 7. Thus, under the present alkaline conditions, the main species are expected to be $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}$. On contrary, the authors in their recent studies have proposed the diperiodatoargentate(III) as $[\text{Ag}(\text{HL})_2]^{x-}$ in which L is a periodate with uncertain number of protons and HL is a protonated periodate of uncertain number of protons⁵. This can be ruled out by considering the alternative form of IO_4^- at pH > 7 which is in the form $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ or $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}$. Hence, DPA could be as $[\text{Ag}(\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6)_2]^-$ or $[\text{Ag}(\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6)_2]^{3-}$ in alkaline medium¹³. Therefore, under the present experimental condition, diperiodatoargentate(III) may be predicted as $[\text{Ag}(\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6)_2]^-$. The similar speciation of periodate in alkali was proposed¹⁴ for diperiodatonickelate(IV).

Osmium(VIII) is known to form different complexes¹⁵ at different OH^- concentrations $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{OsO}_5(\text{OH})]^{3-}$. At higher concentration of OH^- , $[\text{OsO}_5(\text{OH})]^{3-}$ is significant. At lower concentrations of OH^- , as employed in the present study, and since the rate of oxidation increased with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$, it is reasonable that $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ was operative and its formation is important in the reaction. To explain the observed orders the following Scheme 1 is proposed for osmium(VIII) catalysed reaction.

In the prior equilibrium step 1, the $[\text{OH}^-]$ deprotonates the diperiodatoargentate(III) to give a deprotonated diperiodatoargentate(III). In the second step displacement of a ligand, periodate takes place to give free periodate which is evidenced by decrease in the rate with increase in periodate concentration (Table 1). It may be expected that lower Ag^{III} periodate species such as monoperiodatoargentate(III) is more important in the reaction than the diperiodatoargentate(III). The inverse fractional order in $[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6]^{2-}$ might also be due to this reason. In the pre rate determining stage the osmium(VIII) species combines with a molecule of anionic species of 6-aminopenicillanic acid to give an intermediate complex (C), which further reacts with one mole of monoperiodatoargentate(III) in a rate determining step to give free radical derived from 6-aminopenicillanic acid and regeneration of catalyst, osmium(VIII). This free radical derived from 6-aminopenicillanic acid further reacts with another molecule of monoperiodatoargentate(III) species in further fast step to give the products as given in Scheme 1. Spectroscopic evidence for the complex formation between catalyst and substrate was obtained from UV-Vis spectra of 6-aminopenicillanic acid ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), osmium(VIII) ($5.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), OH^- (0.02 mol dm^{-3}), oxidant ($5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and mixture of both. A hypsochromic shift of about 4 nm from 315 nm to 311

Scheme 1

nm in the spectra of osmium(VIII) was observed. However, the Michaelis-Menten plot (Fig. 4) proved the complex formation between catalyst and reductant, which explains less than unit order in 6-aminopenicillanic acid. The complex formation between substrate and catalyst was also observed in literature¹⁶. The rate law for Scheme 1 could be derived as,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{DPA}]}{dt} = \quad (5)$$

$$= \frac{kK_1K_2K_3 [\text{DPA}] [\text{6-APA}]}{[\text{OH}^-] [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{DPA}]} = K_c = \frac{kK_1K_2K_3 [\text{6-APA}]}{[\text{OH}^-] [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]} \quad (7)$$

$$= \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1K_2 [\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2K_3 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{6-APA}] + K_3 [\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] [\text{6-APA}] + K_1K_3 [\text{6-APA}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1K_2 [\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2K_3 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{6-APA}]}$$

The eq. (7) can be rearranged to eq. (8), which is suitable for verification

$$\frac{[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]}{k_c} = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_1K_2K_3 [\text{6-APA}] [\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_2K_3[\text{6-APA}]} + \frac{1}{kK_3 [\text{6-APA}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (8)$$

According to above equation the plots of $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]/k_c$ versus $[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]$, $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]/k_c$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]/k_c$ versus $1/[\text{6-APA}]$ were linear and are found to be so (Fig. 4). From the intercepts and slopes of such plots, the reaction constants K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and k were calculated as $7.2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $1.8 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $8.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The equilibrium constant K_1 is greater than K_2 which may be attributed to the greater tendency of diperiodatoargentate(III) to under go deprotonation compared to the formation of hydrolysed species in alkaline medium.

The thermodynamic quantities for different equilibrium steps, in Scheme 1 can be evaluated as follows. The diperiodatoargentate(III) and hydroxide ion concentrations were varied at different temperatures. The plots are linear as shown in Fig. 4. From the slopes and intercepts, the values of K_1 were calculated at different tempera-

tures. A van't Hoffs plot was made for the variation of K_1 with temperature [i.e. $\log K_1$ versus $1/T$] and the values of the enthalpy of reaction ΔH , entropy of reaction ΔS , and the free energy of reaction ΔG , were calculated. These values are also given in Table 2. A comparison of the later values with those obtained for the slow step of the reaction shows that these values mainly refer to the rate limiting step, supporting the fact that the reaction before the rate determining step is fairly slow and involves a high activation energy¹⁷. In the same manner, K_2 and K_3 values were calculated at different temperatures and the corresponding values of thermodynamic quantities are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of temperature on osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of 6-APA by DPA in aqueous alkaline medium with respect to the slow step of Scheme 1

(A) Effect of temperature		(B) Activation parameters	
Temp. (K)	$k \times 10^{-4}$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	Parameters	Values
288	5.4	E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	26.3
293	7.2	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	23.8
298	8.9	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-70.0
303	9.3	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	44.6
		log A	9.5
(C) Effect of temperature on first, second and third equilibrium step of Scheme 1			
Temp. (K)	K_1 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$K_2 \times 10^{-4}$ (mol dm^{-3})	$K_3 \times 10^{-3}$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
288	5.4	1.0	2.2
293	6.3	1.3	2.1
298	7.2	1.5	1.8
303	8.2	2.1	1.5
(D) Thermodynamic quantities with respect to K_1 , K_2 and K_3			
Thermodynamic quantities	Values from K_1	Values from K_2	Values from K_3
ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	20.1	14.1	-19.5
ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	84.2	41.8	-3.6
ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-4.7	21.5	-18.4

The negative value of ΔS^\ddagger suggests that the intermediate complex is more ordered than the reactants¹⁸. The observed modest enthalpy of activation and a higher rate constant for the slow step indicates that the oxidation presumably occurs via an inner sphere mechanism. This conclusion is supported by earlier observations¹⁹. The catalyst, osmium(VIII) form the complex (C) with the substrate which enhances the reducing property of the substrate than that without catalyst.

Fig. 4. Verification rate law (7) in the form of (8) at different temperatures.

The osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of 6-aminopenicillanic acid by diperiodatoargentate(III) was studied and oxidation products were identified. Among the various species of Ag^{III} in alkaline medium, the diperiodatoargentate(III) was the active species, whereas monoperoargentate(III) itself is considered to be the

active species for the title reaction. The active species of Os^{VIII} is $[OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}$. Activation parameters were evaluated for the catalysed reactions. Catalytic constants and the activation parameters with reference to catalyst were also computed.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade and double distilled water was used throughout the work. A solution of 6-aminopenicillanic acid was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of recrystallized sample in double distilled water. The required concentration of 6-aminopenicillanic acid was used from its aqueous stock solution. The osmium(VIII) solution was prepared by dissolving $\text{OsO}_4^{\text{VIII}}$ oxide (Johnson Matthey) in 0.50 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide. The concentration was ascertained by determining the unreacted $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ with standard Ce^{IV} solution in an acidic medium²⁰. Potassium nitrate and potassium hydroxide (BDH) were used to maintain ionic strength and alkalinity of the reaction. Aqueous solution of silver nitrate was used to study the product effect, Ag^{I} . A stock standard solution of potassium periodate was prepared by dissolving a known weight of potassium periodate (Riedel-de Haen) in hot water and used after 24 h. Its concentration was ascertained iodometrically at neutral pH maintained by using phosphate buffer²¹. The pH of the medium in the solution was measured by [ELICO (LI613)] pH meter.

Diperiodatoargentate(III) was prepared by oxidizing Ag^{I} in the presence of potassium periodate as described elsewhere¹². The mixture of 28 g of potassium hydroxide and 23 g of potassium periodate in 100 cm^3 of water along with 8.5 g silver nitrate was heated just to boiling and 20 g of potassium persulphate was added in several lots with stirring and then allowed to cool. It was filtered through a medium porosity fritted glass filter and 40 g of sodium hydroxide was added slowly to the filtrate, whereupon a voluminous orange precipitate agglomerates. The precipitate is filtered as above and washed three to four times with cold water. The pure crystals were dissolved in 50 cm^3 of water and warmed to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with constant stirring thereby some solid was dissolved to give a red solution. The resulting solution was filtered when it was hot and on cooling at room temperature, the orange crystals separated out and were recrystallized from water. The complex was characterized from its UV spectrum, which exhibited three peaks at 216, 255 and 362 nm. These spectral features were identical to those reported earlier for diperiodatoargentate(III)¹². The magnetic moment study revealed that the complex is diamagnetic. The

compound prepared was analyzed²² for silver and periodate by acidifying a solution of the material with hydrochloric acid, recovering and weighing the silver chloride for Ag and titrating the iodine liberated when excess potassium iodide was added to the filtrate for IO_4^- . The aqueous solution of diperiodatoargentate(III) was used for the required concentration of diperiodatoargentate(III) in the reaction mixture.

All kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions with 6-APA concentration greater than diperiodatoargentate(III) concentration at constant ionic strength of 0.04 mol dm^{-3} . The reaction was initiated by mixing thermally equilibrated ($25.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) solutions of diperiodatoargentate(III), 6-APA, KOH and KNO_3 . Since the initial reaction was too fast to be monitored by usual methods, the course of reaction was followed by monitoring the decrease in absorbance of diperiodatoargentate(III) in a 1 cm quartz cell placed in the thermostatted compartment of a Varian Cary-50 Bio UV-Vis spectrophotometer connected to a rapid kinetic accessory (HI-TECH SFA-12) at its absorption maximum of 360 nm as a function of time. Application of Beer's law has verified between 5.0×10^{-5} and $3.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of diperiodatoargentate(III) at 360 nm under the reaction conditions with the molar extinction coefficient, $\epsilon = 13900 \pm 50 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The kinetic runs were followed for more than 80% completion of the reaction and good first order kinetics were observed. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_c , were determined from the log (absorbance) versus time plots (Fig. 3). The plots were linear over 75% completion of the reaction under the range of OH^- concentration used. The pseudo-first order rate constant for uncatalysed reaction under present experimental condition is $1.97 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The uncatalysed rate constant is very less in comparison with catalysed rate constant. Hence it is neglected. The k_c values were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$ and are the average of at least three independent kinetic runs (Table 1).

During the kinetics a constant concentration, viz. $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of KIO_4 was used throughout the study unless otherwise stated. Since periodate is present in excess in diperiodatoargentate(III), the possibility of oxidation of 6-aminopenicillanic acid by periodate in alkaline medium at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was tested. However, it was found that

there was no significant reaction under the experimental conditions employed compared to the diperiodatoargentate(III) oxidation of 6-aminopenicillanic acid. The total periodate concentration was calculated by considering the periodate present in the diperiodatoargentate(III) solution and that additionally added.

In view of the modest concentration of alkali used in the reaction medium, attention was also directed to the effect of the reaction vessel surface on the kinetics. Use of polythene/acrylic wares and quartz or polyacrylate cells gave the same results, indicating that the surface does not have any significant effect on the reaction rates. In view of the ubiquitous contamination of carbonate in the basic medium, the effect of carbonate was also studied. Added carbonate had no effect on the reaction rates, however fresh solutions were nevertheless used for carrying out in each kinetic run.

References

- 1 D Lalo and M M Mahant, *J Chem Soc , Dalton Trans* , 1990, **13**, 311
- 2 K Bal Reddy B Sethuram and T Navneeth Rao, *Indian J Chem , Sect A*, 1981, **20**, 395
- 3 B Sethuram, "Some Aspects of Electron Transfer Reactions Involving Organic Molecules", Allied Publishers (P) Ltd , New Delhi, 2003, 151
- 4 P K Jaiswal and K L Yadav, *Talanta*, 1970, **17**, 236
- 5 P Jayaprakash Rao, B Sethuram and T Navneeth Rao, *React Kinet Catal* , 1985, **29**, 289
- 6 A Kumar, P Kumar and P Ramamurthy, *Polyhedron*, 1999, **18**, 773
- 7 A K Das, *Coord Chem Rev* , 2001, **213** 307
- 8 M C Agarwal and S K Upadhyay *J Sci Ind Res* , 1983 **42**, 508
- 9 P Veerasomiah, K Bal Reddy, B Sethuram and T Navneeth Rao, *Indian J Chem Sect A* 1987 **26** 402
- 10 C V Hiremath, S D Kulkarni and S T Nandibewoor *Ind Eng Chem Res* , in press
- 11 E A Moelwyn Hughes, 'Kinetics of Reaction in Solutions', Oxford University Press, London, 1947 297
- 12 G L Cohen and G Atkinson, *Inorg Chem* , 1964 **3** 1741
- 13 C E Crouthamel, H V Meek D S Martin and C V Manus, *J Am Chem Soc* , 1949, **71**, 3031
- 14 S Bhattacharya, B Saha, A Datta and P Banerjee *Coord Chem Rev* , 1988, **47**, 170
- 15 D L Kamble and S T Nandibewoor *J Phys Org Chem* , 1998, **11**, 171
- 16 R V Hosahalli, A P Savanur, S T Nandibewoor and S A Chimatadar, *Transition Met Chem* 2010 **35**, 237
- 17 K S Rangappa, M P Raghavendra D S Mahadevappa and D Channegouda, *J Org Chem* 1998, **63**, 531
- 18 A Weissberger, in E S Lewis (ed), 'Investigations of Rates and Mechanism of Reactions in Techniques of Chemistry', Vol 4, Wiley, New York 1974, 421
- 19 M Martinez, M A Pitarque and R V Eldik *J Chem Soc , Dalton Trans* , 1996, **14**, 2665
- 20 O C Sexena, *Microchem J* , 1967, **12**, 609
- 21 G P Panigrahi and P K Misro, *Indian J Chem Sect A*, 1977, **15**, 1066
- 22 G H Jeffery, J Bassett, J Mendham and R C Denney, "Vogel's Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed , ELBS, Longman Singapore Publishers Pvt Ltd , Singapore, 1996, 467